

Parametric study of a vibro-impact wave energy converter

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Abstract: In this study, a non-linear vibro-impact mechanism is integrated inside a semi-submerged cylindrical heaving point absorber in order to enhance its power capture by utilising the non-linearity of vibro-impact events. A piece-wise linear model is derived considering linear wave-bouy interaction and the non-linear vibro-impact mechanism. Since the dynamics and performance of the vibro-impact wave energy converter (WEC) are sensitive to design parameters, a parametric study and analysis are conducted numerically by varying the design parameters in a broad range to evaluate their influence on the vibro-impact WEC's dynamics and performance, in terms of response amplitude operator, average power output and peak-to-average power ratio. Numerical simulations show that there exist some optimal sets of the design parameters to achieve a trade-off among the aforementioned performance indices. Hence, the parametric study in this paper can give some basic guidelines for optimising and prototyping the design of the vibro-impact WEC for wave tank testing.

Keywords: Wave Energy Conversion, Heaving Point Absorber, Vibro-Impact Mechanism, Non-linear Power Take-Off, Parametric Study.

1. INTRODUCTION

To harvest energy from ocean waves, various technologies and devices have been examined (Drew et al., 2009; Babarit et al., 2012; Falcão, 2010). These wave energy converters (WECs) can be classified into the following five predominant types: oscillating water columns, attenuators, point absorbers (PAs), terminators, and over-topping devices. Among the aforementioned WECs, a heaving PA may be one of the simplest and most promising concepts (Ricci et al., 2009), since it is easy to install and economic to operate. PAs can be categorised into three subtypes, including (i) one-body PAs, e.g. the CETO buoy, (ii) two-body PAs, e.g. the Wavebob buoy and the OPT's PowerBuoy, and (iii) PA arrays, e.g. the WaveStar device.

These PAs can harvest energy efficiently when resonance occurs. However, PAs' natural bandwidths are narrow, whilst wave spectra are generally broader. One way to maximise power absorption of WECs across a wide frequency range is to utilise control approaches (Ringwood et al., 2014). Another way is to design novel WEC concepts or power take-off (PTO) systems. Some non-linear PTO concepts have the potential to improve power capture width and to widen resonance bandwidth. For example, Bailey (2010) investigated the influence of non-linear PTO dampers on WECs' power capture by numerical and experimental testing. In addition to non-linear dampers, Zhang

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of a vibro-impact mechanism integrated inside a cylindrical heaving point absorber.

et al. (2014) proposed a bi-stable mechanical system, consisting of two symmetrically oblique springs, to achieve negative stiffness by a snap-through mechanism. Based on the same principle, CorPower Ocean invented a “negative” spring, termed WaveSpring, to increase WECs' response bandwidth (Todalshaug et al., 2016). These studies conclude that a properly designed non-linear PTO system has the potential to maximise power absorption over a wide range of wave frequencies.

This study proposes a vibro-impact WEC which uses a non-linear vibro-impact mechanism to enhance power capture and to broaden its bandwidth. As shown in Fig. 1, a semi-submerged cylindrical buoy (M_b) is excited by incident waves, and oscillates as a result. An inner mass

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(M_m) is connected to the buoy by a linear PTO damper (c) and a supporting spring (k_1), and oscillates accordingly due to the interaction force with the buoy. The supporting spring is prestressed to balance the inner mass at its equilibrium point with a suitable original length. The key mechanism is that the up and down impact springs (k_2), attached to the top and floor of the buoy induce vibro-impact events when the relative displacement between the inner mass and buoy exceeds the up or down gaps (G). The non-linear vibro-impact events increase the WEC's complexity, but have the potential to improve the WEC's power capture bandwidth.

In this paper, a mathematical model to describe the dynamics of the vibro-impact WEC is derived, and parametric studies are conducted to understand how the design parameters, including M_m , k_1 , k_2 , G and c , influence the WEC's dynamics and power absorption under regular wave conditions. Numerical simulations demonstrate that: (i) The response amplitude operator (RAO) of the relative motion between the inner mass and the buoy acts like a "band-pass filter", with relatively small gain value when the wave frequency is low. As extreme sea states are typically characterised by low frequency, the vibro-impact WEC is inherently decoupled and shows high reliability and survivability under extreme sea states. (ii) The non-linear dynamics and power absorption of the vibro-impact WEC are sensitive to the design parameters. Hence, the system performance, in terms of relative RAO and average power output, can be optimised by adjusting M_m , k_1 , k_2 , G and c . (iii) Occurrence of impacts may increase the peak-to-average power ratio of the PTO under certain settings, but the peak-to-average power ratio can be constrained, even reduced, by design optimisation.

The remainder of the paper is organised as follows: Section 2 details the wave-buoy interaction, whilst the vibro-impact mechanism is detailed in Section 3. Section 4 discusses the parametric studies to investigate how the design parameters influence the dynamics and performance of the vibro-impact WEC. Some concluding remarks are drawn up in Section 5.

2. WAVE-BUOY INTERACTION

As shown in Fig. 1, a cylindrical buoy is considered, and its radius, height and draft are $r = 1$ m, $h = 2$ m, and $d = 1$ m, respectively. As this study mainly focuses on how the design parameters influence the dynamics and performance of the vibro-impact WEC, the buoy's motion is constrained to heave mode only. Therefore, the dynamics of the buoy are governed by

$$M_b \ddot{z}_b = f_e + f_r + f_{hs} + f_i, \quad (1)$$

where f_e , f_r and f_{hs} represent the excitation, radiation and hydrostatic forces, respectively. f_i represents the interaction force between the inner mass and buoy. M_b , z_b and \ddot{z}_b are the buoy mass, heave displacement and acceleration, respectively.

For the buoy in Fig. 1, the hydrostatic force is given as

$$f_{hs} = -\rho g \pi r^2 z_b, \quad (2)$$

where ρ and g are the water density and gravity constant, respectively. The radiation force, in the time-domain, is written as

$$f_r = -m_\infty \ddot{z}_b - k_r * \dot{z}_b, \quad (3)$$

where m_∞ , k_r and \dot{z}_b are the added mass at infinite frequency, the impulse response function (IRF) of the radiation force, and the velocity of the buoy in heave, respectively. The symbol $*$ represents the convolution operator. The hydrodynamic coefficients are computed using the boundary element method code NEMOH (Babarit and Delhommeau, 2015), and the radiation IRF is shown in Fig. 2(a).

Here, we define f_{rc} , representing the convolution term of the radiation force in Eq. (3), as

$$f_{rc} = k_r * \dot{z}_b. \quad (4)$$

Finite order approximations of the radiation force were studied by Guo et al. (2017b); Faedo et al. (2018), in which the convolution term can be approximated by

$$\dot{x}_r = A_r x_r + B_r \dot{z}_b, \quad (5)$$

$$f_{rc} \approx C_r x_r, \quad (6)$$

where $x_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ is the state vector for the identified system. $A_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B_r \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$, $C_r \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$ are the system matrices. n is the dynamical order which is selected by trial and error via evaluating the goodness of fit, defined by the normalised mean square-error (Guo et al., 2017b). In this study, $n = 4$ is used, and the goodness of fit is 0.9998. A_r , B_r and C_r are given in the Appendix.

The excitation force can be determined quantitatively by its frequency response function (FRF), represented as

$$F_e(j\omega) = H_e(j\omega)A(j\omega), \quad (7)$$

where $H_e(j\omega)$ is the FRF of the excitation force and $A(j\omega)$ is the frequency-domain representation of incident wave $\eta(t)$. In Fig. 2(b), the excitation FRF is represented by its amplitude response $|H_e(j\omega)|$ and phase response $\angle H_e(j\omega)$. Alternatively, the excitation force can be rewritten in the time-domain as

$$f_e(t) = k_e(t) * \eta(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} k_e(t - \tau) \eta(\tau) d\tau, \quad (8)$$

where $k_e(t)$ is the excitation force IRF related to the FRF $H_e(j\omega)$, given as

$$k_e(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H_e(j\omega) e^{j\omega t} d\omega. \quad (9)$$

Based on excitation FRF in Fig. 2(b), the excitation IRF $k_e(t)$ is represented by the black dash-dot curve in Fig. 2(c). However, $k_e(t)$ is non-causal since $k_e(t) \neq 0$ for $t < 0$ (see the shadowed area in Fig. 2(c)).

Causalisation and approximation of the excitation were studied by Guo et al. (2017a, 2018), in which a time-shifting technique was applied to causalise the non-causal kernel function $k_e(t)$ to its causalised form $k_{e,c}(t)$ with causalisation time t_c ($t_c \geq 0$). Thus, wave prediction with a horizon of t_c is required. According to the time shift property of the convolution operator, the causalised system with wave prediction gives the same excitation force of the non-causal system, since

$$f_e(t) = k_e(t) * \eta(t) \quad (10)$$

$$= k_e(t - t_c) * \eta(t + t_c) = k_{e,c}(t) * \eta_p(t), \quad (11)$$

where $k_{e,c}(t) = k_e(t - t_c)$ and $\eta_p(t) = \eta(t + t_c)$ are the causalised excitation IRF (see the red solid curve in Fig. 2(c)) and the predicted wave elevation advanced by t_c , respectively.

Fig. 2. (a) Radiation IRFs, (b) excitation FRF and (c) excitation IRFs. In (b), the excitation FRF is represented by its amplitude response $|H_e(j\omega)|$ and phase response $\angle H_e(j\omega)$.

Similarly, Eq. (11) can be approximated by the following state-space model

$$\dot{x}_e = A_e x_e + B_e \eta_p, \quad (12)$$

$$f_e \approx C_e x_e + D_e \eta_p, \quad (13)$$

where $x_e \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$ is the state vector for the excitation system. $A_e \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B_e \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times 1}$, $C_e \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$ and $D_e \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 1}$ are the system matrices, and n is the order. t_c and n are selected by trial and error via evaluating the truncation error and goodness of fit, defined by Guo et al. (2018). In this study, $t_c = 3.2$ s and $n = 6$ are selected, and the identified excitation IRF is compared with the causalised excitation IRF in Fig. 2(c) with a truncation error of less than 0.0073 and a goodness of fit of 0.9953.

3. VIBRO-IMPACT MECHANISM

For the inner mass, its equation of motion is given as

$$M_m \ddot{z}_m = -f_i, \quad (14)$$

where M_m , z_m and \ddot{z}_m represent the inner mass, and its displacement and acceleration in heave, respectively. The interaction force f_i depends on the relative displacement between the inner mass and buoy, $z_r = z_m - z_b$. As shown in Fig. 3(a), when the relative displacement is larger than or equal to the gap G , that is $z_r \geq G$, the supporting spring (k_1), the up impact spring (k_2), and the PTO damper (c) are active. Therefore, f_i can be written as

$$f_i = k_1 z_r + k_2 (z_r - G) + c v_r, \quad (15)$$

where $v_r = \dot{z}_r$ represent the relative velocity.

Fig. 3. Three operation modes of the vibro-impact WEC.

As shown in Fig. 3(b), when $G > z_r > -G$, the supporting spring (k_1) and the PTO damper (c) are active. Therefore, f_i can be written as

$$f_i = k_1 z_r + c v_r. \quad (16)$$

For the case $z_r \leq -G$ in Fig. 3(c), the supporting spring (k_1), the down impact spring (k_2), and the PTO damper (c) are active. Hence, f_i can be written as

$$f_i = k_1 z_r + k_2 (z_r + G) + c v_r. \quad (17)$$

4. PARAMETRIC STUDY

The dynamics and performance of the vibro-impact WEC are sensitive to the design parameters, including M_m , k_1 , k_2 , G , and c . In this section, parametric studies are conducted to investigate how these parameters influence the vibro-impact WEC's performance. For clarity, regular wave condition, with wave height H and frequency ω , is considered. To evaluate the dynamics of the vibro-impact WEC, the relative RAO is defined as

$$RAO_r = \frac{2 \max(z_r)}{H}. \quad (18)$$

In this study, a pure damper is used as the PTO device. To evaluate the performance of the vibro-impact WEC, the instantaneous power P_i , average power P_a and peak-to-average power ratio P_{p2a} are defined as

$$P_i = c v_r^2, \quad (19)$$

$$P_a = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T P_i dt, \quad (20)$$

$$P_{p2a} = \frac{\max(P_i)}{P_a}, \quad (21)$$

where T is the wave period. The following subsections will detail how these design parameters influence the relative RAO, average power, and peak-to-average power ratio.

4.1 Influence of Inner Mass

The influence of the inner mass on the relative RAO, average power, and peak-to-average power ratio are shown in Fig. 4. As shown in Figs. 4(a)-(b), the relative RAO and average power are characterised by a band-pass effect, where the bandwidth is sensitive to the variation in the inner mass. The bandwidth initially increases and then decrease as M_m increases from 200 kg to 3000 kg, while the resonance frequency decreases monotonically. In Fig. 4(c), the maximal and minimal values of the peak-to-average power ratio are 3.5 and 1.5, respectively. That is, the peak-to-average power ratio can be either amplified or attenuated by the vibro-impact mechanism, depending on design parameter values and wave conditions. Therefore, $M_m \in [750, 1500]$ kg is preferred to achieve a large relative RAO, a high average power, a broad bandwidth, and a low peak-to-average power ratio, simultaneously.

Fig. 4. (a) Relative RAOs, (b) average power outputs, and (c) peak-to-average power ratios, with $M_m \in [200, 3000]$ kg, $\omega \in [0.06, 6.28]$ rad/s, $k_1 = 5000$ N/m, $k_2 = 20000$ N/m, $G = 0.8$ m, $c = 1000$ Ns/m, and $H = 0.8$ m. $M_m + M_b = M_t = \rho\pi r^2 d$ is applied to constrain the draft at the equilibrium point.

Fig. 5. (a) Relative RAOs, (b) average power outputs, and (c) peak-to-average power ratios, with $k_1 \in [300, 60000]$ N/m, $\omega \in [0.06, 6.28]$ rad/s, $M_m = 1500$ kg, $k_2 = 20000$ N/m, $G = 0.8$ m, $c = 1000$ Ns/m, and $H = 0.8$ m.

4.2 Influence of Stiffness

By adjusting k_1 , the vibro-impact WEC's dynamics and performance vary significantly, as shown in Fig. 5. As shown in Figs. 5(a)-(b), the resonance frequency increases slightly as k_1 increases, while the bandwidth of the relative RAO and average power output decreases significantly. In Fig. 5(c), the peak-to-average power ratio is low, with a maximum value of 3 and a minimum value of 1.5. $k_1 \in [5000, 20000]$ N/m is preferred for achieving a trade-off among the relative RAO, average power, capture bandwidth, and peak-to-average power ratio.

Variation in k_2 has little influence on the dynamics and performance of the vibro-impact WEC, which is illustrated in Fig. 6. The relative RAO, average power, bandwidth and peak-to-average power ratio are robust to the change of k_2 . Meanwhile, harder impact springs are preferred for end-protection. Therefore, the suitable region is $k_2 \in [50000, 200000]$ N/m. Comparing Figs. 5 and 6, it is clear that the dynamics and performance of the vibro-impact WEC are more sensitive to the stiffness of the supporting spring than the impact springs.

4.3 Influence of Gap

Variation in G does not affect the bandwidth of the relative RAO and average power, but has significant influence on their maximum values, as shown in Figs. 7(a)-(b). A small G leads to a small relative RAO and a low average power, since impact events occur periodically and the relative motion is constrained by the impact springs with large stiffness. Consequently, the peak-to-average power ratio is large, mainly due to the low average power output. In contrast to the other design parameters, Fig. 7(c) illustrates that the peak-to-average power ratio is critically sensitive to the variation in G . Therefore, a large G is preferred to achieve a large relative RAO, a high average power and a small peak-to-average power ratio, simultaneously. However, the upper gap limit is bounded by physical constraints, e.g. the buoy height. For this case study, the preferred values are $G \in [0.4, 0.8]$ m.

4.4 Influence of Damping Coefficient

The PTO damping coefficient has a large influence on the dynamics and performance of the vibro-impact WEC,

Fig. 6. (a) Relative RAOs, (b) average power outputs, and (c) peak-to-average power ratios, with $k_2 \in [5000, 600000]$ N/m, $\omega \in [0.06, 6.28]$ rad/s, $M_m = 1500$ kg, $k_1 = 10000$ N/m, $G = 0.8$ m, $c = 1000$ Ns/m, and $H = 0.8$ m.

Fig. 7. (a) Relative RAOs, (b) average power outputs, and (c) peak-to-average power ratios, with $G \in [0.04, 0.96]$ m, $\omega \in [0.06, 6.28]$ rad/s, $M_m = 1500$ kg, $k_1 = 10000$ N/m, $k_2 = 200000$ N/m, $c = 1000$ Ns/m, and $H = 0.8$ m.

as shown in Fig. 8, where a large damping coefficient results in a small relative RAO and a narrow bandwidth. However, the resonance frequency appears to be unaffected by the PTO damping coefficient. As shown in Fig. 8(b), the average power output is low and the bandwidth is narrow when the damping coefficient is less than 800 Ns/m. The bandwidth appears to be unaffected by the damping coefficient when it is larger than 1500 Ns/m. Fig. 8(c) also shows that the peak-to-average power ratio tends to small values when the damping coefficient is larger than 1500 Ns/m. Therefore, the preferred damping coefficient values are within $c \in [1500, 2500]$ Ns/m to obtain a large relative RAO, a high average power output, a wide bandwidth, and a low peak-to-average power ratio, simultaneously.

5. CONCLUSION

In this work, a mathematical model of the vibro-impact WEC is derived. Parametric studies are conducted by numerical simulations, which illustrate that the vibro-impact WEC's dynamics and performance, in terms of relative RAO, average power output and peak-to-average power ratio, are sensitive to variations in the design

parameters, including the inner mass, spring stiffness, impact gaps and PTO damping coefficient.

Regardless of how these parameters vary, the relative RAO is characterised by a band-pass effect. Hence, the relative RAO is small when the wave frequency is low, indicating high system survivability under extreme sea states, which generally consist of low frequencies. The average power output is sensitive to all the design parameters, while the peak-to-average power ratio seem to be only affected significantly by the impact gap. The bandwidth of the relative RAO and average power output is sensitive to the variations in the inner mass, stiffness of the primary spring, and insensitive to the variations in the stiffness of the impact springs, impact gap, and PTO damping coefficient. These parametric studies give some basic guidelines for the design of a vibro-impact WEC.

Design optimisation is required to find some sets of the design parameters to achieve a large relative RAO, a high average power output, a wide power capture bandwidth, and a low peak-to-average power ratio. Ongoing work focuses on design optimisation of the proposed vibro-impact WEC to match a specific wave spectrum by panchromatic

Fig. 8. (a) Relative RAOs, (b) average power outputs, and (c) peak-to-average power ratios, with $c \in [150, 4000]$ Ns/m, $\omega \in [0.06, 6.28]$ rad/s, $M_m = 1500$ kg, $k_1 = 10000$ N/m, $k_2 = 200000$ N/m, $G = 0.6$ m, and $H = 0.8$ m.

analysis, and on prototyping of a small scale vibro-impact WEC for wave tank testing.

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Appendix A. PARAMETERS

Simulation conditions are: buoy radius $r = 1$ m, height $h = 2$ m, draft $d = 1$ m, total mass of the buoy and inner mass $M_t = M_b + M_m = 3,220.13$ kg, water density $\rho = 1,025$ kg/m³, gravity constant $g = 9.81$ N/kg, added mass at infinite frequency $m_\infty = 1,883.47$ kg, and wave height $H = 0.8$ m.

The system matrices in Eqs. (5) and (6) are

$$A_r = \begin{bmatrix} -1.50, & -2.06, & 1.54, & -0.35 \\ 2.06, & -0.01, & 0.07, & -0.02 \\ -1.54, & 0.07, & -2.38, & 1.96 \\ -0.35, & 0.02, & -1.96, & -0.51 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$B_r = [-403.88, 22.57, -181.05, -49.82]^T,$$

$$C_r = [-4.04, -0.23, 1.81, -0.50].$$

The system matrices in Eqs. (12) and (13) are

$$A_e = \begin{bmatrix} -0.05, & -0.61, & -0.13, & -0.24, & -0.13, & -0.12 \\ 0.61, & -0.19, & -1.13, & -0.29, & -0.39, & -0.24 \\ -0.13, & 1.13, & -0.39, & -1.56, & -0.47, & -0.52 \\ 0.24, & -0.29, & 1.56, & -0.62, & -2.04, & -0.66 \\ -0.13, & 0.39, & -0.47, & 2.04, & -0.88, & -2.38 \\ 0.12, & -0.24, & 0.52, & -0.66, & 2.38, & -1.21 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$B_e = [-549.4, 884.3, -1008.7, 939.5, -784.6, 603.3]^T,$$

$$C_e = [-5.49, -8.84, -10.09, -9.39, -7.85, -6.03],$$

$$D_e = [49.85].$$